

FOOD AND SERVICES SECTORS IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES. CASE STUDY OF MOUNTAIN AREA

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Abstract

The research underscores the significance of the food and accommodation sectors within Central and Eastern European countries, with a specific focus on the mountainous regions. The study draws insights from selected European areas, specifically the Austrian Tyrol and the North-East of Romania. An examination of Eurostat indicators reveals a positive trend in entrepreneurship within the Central and Eastern European countries. This positive dynamic is often fueled by a swift desire for financial gain, sometimes at the expense of considering the contextual nuances of dietary behaviors and service provision under normal conditions. Notably, mountain entrepreneurs may, at times, prioritize expedient and unsustainable earnings over quality. The research utilizes data sourced from

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Eurostat, employing Excel and SPSS for processing, and adopts analytical models akin to those found in existing literature.

Keywords: sustainability of the mountain area; Austrian Tyrol region; North-East region of Romania; food and accommodation sectors

1. Introduction

This study focuses on the food and accommodation sector, undertaking an analysis of mountain entrepreneurship to propose solutions for the sustainability of agribusiness. Relevant Eurostat entrepreneurship indicators from Austria and select Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, including Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia, are considered. The analysis spans the period 2011-2017, with specific intervals receiving due attention. Case studies involve recognized mountain products, with a detailed examination of entrepreneurship in the mountain regions of Austria, specifically Tyrol, and Romania's North-East. (Benaki et al., 2007; Blazkova et al., 2016; Pavolova et al., 2021)

2. Results and data

During the examined timeframe, the specific indicator for the food and accommodation sectors is the population of active enterprises. Notable increases in this indicator were observed in Bulgaria (3.37%), Croatia (8.92%), Lithuania (51.67%), Romania (34.52%), Slovakia (1.96%), Estonia (12.42% between 2015-2017), and Poland (5.61% between 2016-2017). Conversely, Austria experienced a decrease of -7.15%, the Czech Republic - 6.35% (between 2013-2017), Hungary -10.67% (between 2011-2017), and Latvia -0.44% (between 2016-2017) in the population of active enterprises.

The fluctuations observed in the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries prompted a comparative investigation between two distinct European entrepreneurship types, namely Tyrol (Austria) and Northeast (Romania). Tyrol, a pivotal Austrian region for food and accommodation services, encompasses Außerfern, Innsbruck, Osttirol, Tiroler Oberland, and Tiroler Unterland. In contrast, the Northeast, an emerging region in Romania, comprises Bacau, Botosani, Iasi, Neamt, Suceava, and Vaslui. Although the Austrian population of active enterprises and their respective regions experienced a decline, specifically Tirol (-6.04%), Außerfern (-

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5.63%), Innsbruck (-6.32%), Osttirol (-10.56%), Tiroler Oberland (-2.23%), and Tiroler Unterland (-8.14%), Romanian regions and counties witnessed an increase in the population of active enterprises: North-East (87.77%), Bacau (53.60%), Botosani (105.67%), Iasi (68.45%), Neamt (81.41%), Suceava (120.74%), and Vaslui (117.55%). Similar trends were observed in other CEE countries.

Considering the benefits of mountain products, entrepreneurs are encouraged to develop businesses in mountainous regions. Over the analyzed period, the CEE countries with the highest growth in entrepreneurship within the accommodation and food services sector were the Czech Republic (58085 units in 2017), Poland (82147 units in 2017), and Romania (37926 units in 2017). The population of active enterprises in t – number fluctuated in the period 2013-2018 in Austria (-11.54%), Bulgaria (3.26%), Czech Republic (-5.13%), Estonia (25.33%), Croatia (17.95%), Hungary (2.18%), Lithuania (35.99%), Latvia (18.21%), Poland (-13.87%), Romania (10.22%), and Slovakia (9.40%). These CEE countries exhibited considerable and noteworthy fluctuations or linearity in this context (figure 1). The extent of this growth's sustainability remains uncertain, with some studies suggesting that it might involve increased consumption of high-fat or artificially grown foods, potentially compromising quality.

Fig. 1: Population of active enterprises in CEE countries (Accommodation and food services sectors)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Despite Austria showcasing a marginal decline in the population of active enterprises index during the 2008-2017 period, it still serves as a benchmark for the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries (figure 2).

Fig. 2: Population of active enterprises in Austria and Romania, respectively
Austrian Tyrol and Romanian North-East (Accommodation and food
services sectors)

Source: Designed by authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography
Statistics

Austria, surrounded by Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, serves as a model for other economies due to its provision of higher-quality services and food behaviors. The Austrian population of active enterprises experienced a decrease from 2008 to 2017, declining by -4130 units (from 57726 units to 53596). In contrast, the Romanian population of active enterprises saw an increase from 2011 to 2017, growing by 9732 units (from 28194 units to 37926). This trend was similarly observed in Tyrol, the region with the highest mountain potential in Austria, although the intensity of the decrease varied. Specifically, the population of active enterprises in Tyrol declined by -688 units (from 11394 units to 10706). Conversely, in the North-East region of Romania, the degree of entrepreneurship increased by 2469 units (from 2813 units to 5282).

3. Conclusion

The selected mountain products and regions stand as representative examples for Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries. Within this framework, the authors posit that mountain entrepreneurship presents viable solutions for sustainable growth. As previously articulated, the authors assert that a comparative analysis between Austrian Tyrol and the North-East region of Romania is warranted due to shared geographical features (mountainous regions and predominantly rural areas) and comparable socio-economic conditions. The entrepreneurial landscapes in these two countries and regions exhibit noteworthy parallels.

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